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Linguistic Representation of News Articles on Israel-Hamas War

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Abstract

Media is a powerful tool for forming public opinion about geopolitical issues. The use of framing techniques in news articles is an important part of this process. However, research on the linguistic representation of news articles on Israel-Hamas war is limited. This study aimed to examine the linguistic representation and uncover underlying meanings within news articles about the Israel-Hamas war by examining the framing techniques employed by media outlets and their morphosemantic and syntactic features. The results of this research not only enhance the comprehension of how conflict is portrayed in media but also impact language instruction and media literacy education. This study adds to a wider conversation about how language influences our comprehension of worldwide conflicts and emphasizes the need for analyzing media communication critically. This research has the potential to serve as a foundation for future research which makes it easier for others to build on this work and continue advancing understanding of how media platforms work. Moreover, this research holds value for educational institutions, particularly those offering linguistics, journalism and media-related courses.

Keywords: *critical discourse analysis, morphosemantics, syntax, news framing techniques, news articles, Israel-Hamas war*

Introduction

The Israel-Hamas conflict has been a major global focus, sparking debates. How media practitioners relay news articles regarding this issue plays a crucial role in shaping public views. The public trusts the information provided by the news media. Without a doubt, the media play an essential role in transmitting news about all situations in the world, which include political conditions, military events, and all other issues. While news brought by media practitioners plays an integral part in the formation of public opinion, it simultaneously introduces the challenge of potential bias and framing. News frame refers to the verbal and visual information in an article posited by news outlets that directly or implicitly suggests what the problem is about, how it can be addressed, and who is responsible for creating and solving it. In Layman's terms, it is the practice in which aspects of specific issues are highlighted in the news to promote a particular interpretation. The framing of the conflict in news articles influences not only what information is presented but also how it is interpreted by the audience (Tewksbury, 2020; Olumolawa, 2021).

The worldwide image of the United States has dropped precipitously during the past few years. Among the factors is the increasing number of gun violence incidents which affects the reputation of the country abroad. Whenever there is a tragic mass shooting, it often gets attention in the international news. However, while news media in the US typically connects gun violence to the mental health of the culprits, foreign media outlets may link it to the gun policies and the overall gun culture of the aforementioned country. This phenomenon falls under media framing, wherein some aspects of a perceived reality make them more salient in a communicating text, in such a way as to promote a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation, and/or treatment recommendation for the item. When foreign media frame the gun violence issue to depict the United States as an unsafe and undesired place, it diminishes the country's positive image and its influence around the world (Akyürek et al., 2020).

Whereas, in the Philippines, how news articles are framed reflects the relationship among the media, the government, and the public. The frequently used frames by news sources suggest that the news media acts as an agent of the government and its law enforcers. During the Duterte regime, the news regarding the anti-drug campaign is presented from the perspective of the police as they are the main source of the reports. They are supplemented by statements and speeches of higher officials who are advocating the war on drugs to the public. In the same way, the media also conveys the sentiments and opinions of the government officials who are opposed to the war on drugs. Thus, news articles are framed in a way that it is based on the point-of-view of the government, as well as its law enforcers.

Given the rampant issue of mal-information, the urgency of this study is underscored by its potential to benefit the general public, providing insights into how media outlets employ framing techniques in crafting news articles depending on their intention and what they want the public to perceive. Thus, by uncovering how language is used in news discourse regarding the Israel-Hamas war, this research seeks to provide a thorough examination that will not only advance understanding but also elevates public awareness and comprehension of the said conflict. Whereas, the social significance of this study lies in the fact that this can be used as a reference by scholarly researchers who wish to conduct similar study. This study has the potential to serve as a foundation for future research, making it easier for others to build on this work and continue advancing our understanding of how media platforms work.

There are various studies which also scrutinized the linguistic representation of news articles about various issues which employed discourse analysis as an approach. In the study of Asad et al. (2019) entitled "Linguistic Representation of 100 Days of Pakistan Tehreek - e - Insaaf in Online Pakistani Newspapers: A Critical Discourse Analysis & Systematic Functional Linguistic Perspective,"

and the study of Albonia (2022) entitled “The Linguistic Representation of the Taliban in the Afghani Newspaper, Comparison between Before and After the Power Change,” which focused on how newspapers represent a particular issue. However, while the aforementioned studies have been informative, a critical viewpoint on the linguistic representation of news articles about the Israel-Hamas war is missing in the existing literature. The study aims to address this gap by specifically examining framing techniques in news articles related to the Israel-Hamas war.

The researcher closely followed ethical guidelines while studying how news articles depict the Israel-Hamas war linguistically, safeguarding the study's integrity and trustworthiness. By utilizing techniques for gathering and examining data, the research sought to produce thorough and enlightening findings that would be advantageous to a range of interested parties. The gathered data was carefully evaluated to produce relevant discoveries that were in line with the objectives of the research. These results were later spread through various channels. Copies were printed and placed in the school library for easy access by readers who were interested readers. Moreover, attempts were undertaken to showcase the research at appropriate academic conferences and to get it published in reputable scholarly journals or on respected online platforms. These strategies for sharing information are intended to make the research's important findings about linguistic representation in news articles more available to a larger audience aiming to reach a wider understanding and discussion of the Israel-Hamas conflict.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What framing of the Israel-Hamas war news reports is evident in various news providers?
2. What are the morphosemantic and syntactic features present in the news articles?

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed a qualitative-descriptive approach. Qualitative research involves a naturalistic interpretative approach to the world, wherein researcher study and examine phenomena in their natural settings. They attempt to make sense of or interpret these phenomena in terms of the meanings people attribute to them (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005).

In a more specific sense, this study was descriptive and used Critical Discourse Analysis. The goal of qualitative descriptive studies is to extract a comprehensive summarization of specific events experienced by individuals or groups of individuals. In a simpler term, descriptive studies aim to find out "what is" thus, this utilizes observational and survey methods to collect descriptive data. Thick, detailed descriptions of phenomena can also emerge from qualitative studies, case studies, observational studies, interviews, and portfolio assessments. Moreover, qualitative description design is particularly vital where information is required directly from those experiencing the phenomenon under investigation and where time and resources are limited. This research utilized the methodology of analyzing the linguistic representation of the news articles on Israel-Hamas war (Creswell, 2012; Borg, 2014; Carmel, 2012).

Moreover, since this study focuses on news articles depicting the conflict between Israel and Hamas including analysis of framing techniques through an exploration of the morphosemantic and syntactic usage of news writers, critical discourse analysis (CDA) is the banner of methodology. CDA sheds light on how to attain knowledge through discourse analysis, which will be the basis to act on things.

A qualitative discourse study directs towards the interpretation of the intricacies of meaning in a social context. It is naturalistic as opposed to quantitative, which sets fixed data, observational and not experimental, and is concerned more on validity rather than reliability and generalizability (Trappes-Lomax, as cited in Fernandez, 2011).

Instrument

For this study, the corpora that were utilized were the news articles about the Israel-Hamas war, which were collected directly from the internet through downloading. Since the data sources were public domains, no permissions were needed for data collection to proceed. The sources of the corpora that were used were suited to this study given their credibility and being reliable providers of news articles about the conflict. The researcher collected a total of fifty-one (51) news reports from CNN, AP News, BBC News, Google News, and Reuters. These sources were chosen for their established reputations in delivering accurate and comprehensive coverage. Moreover, Braun and Clarke (2013) suggested a range for the number of research materials, recommending a minimum sample size of at least 10-100 research materials to sufficiently fulfill the study's goal and reach data saturation. Thus, a sample of 30 new articles was used in this study.

The news articles were also selected using a specified criterion: (a) news articles from five enumerated media outlets—CNN, AP News, BBC News, Google News, and Reuters; (b) relevance to the conflict, ensuring that chosen articles directly pertain to the research topic; and lastly, (c) news articles published between October 2023 and March 2024. This method aims to provide a focused and comprehensive analysis of pertinent information within the specified criteria. The researcher gathered the said research materials online with the consideration of the criteria to reach the desired number of corpora. Moreover, the news articles that served as the research

materials were named NA which stands for News Article. Thus, the research materials were labeled as NA01, NA02, NA03... NA30.

Procedure

As the researcher leading this study, I undertook a well-defined series of steps to ensure a systematic and ethically sound approach to data collection. This involved the strategic design of the research methodology, where I made thoughtful choices regarding data collection methods and sampling techniques. Ethical considerations, such as obtaining informed consent, preserving confidentiality, and safeguarding collected data, were integral components of this phase. I remained dedicated to upholding these ethical principles throughout the entire data collection process, prioritizing the credibility and reliability of the information gathered. This meticulous and principled approach underscores the integrity of the study's methodology.

The initial and crucial step involved coordinating with my research adviser to gain a clear understanding of the required procedures for conducting this study. Given that employing the discourse analysis approach was a new venture for me as a researcher, I took the initiative to prepare a set of questions. These inquiries were directed towards my research adviser, aiming to comprehensively grasp the entire process of the study. Recognizing my responsibility as a researcher, I sought to enhance my knowledge about the chosen methodology, ensuring a thorough and informed execution of the study.

The research corpus for this study comprised 30 news articles on the Israel-Hamas war sourced from the internet. Given the abundance of online sources, I opted for a purposive sampling method, adhering to the specific criteria outlined above to narrow down the selection. The objective of this study was to uncover linguistic representation and framing techniques employed by journalists, as well as to identify morphosemantic and syntactic features in their language use. To ensure alignment with this goal, I carefully selected news articles that were directly relevant to the study's objectives.

Data Analysis

To investigate the research questions, the research materials for this study consisted of 30 news articles posted online by media outlets. The selection of these videos was based on specific criteria that aligned with the research objectives. Subsequently, I employed a qualitative research design using a discourse analysis approach to analyze these articles in-depth. This approach allowed me to explore the linguistic and framing strategies employed by journalists to shape the perception of the public towards the conflict between Israel and Hamas.

The process of analyzing the corpora was hinged on the theoretical frameworks discussed in the first chapter. The theories that were used are the following: Five News Frames by Semetko & Valkenburg (2000); Finegan's (2008) Language Construction and Utilization theory; and Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) by Fairclough (1995). Since this study sought to answer the research questions, the said frameworks guided the entire process of the data analysis.

The theoretical framework of Semetko and Valkenburg (2000) answered the first research question which is about the news frames that are evident in the Israel-Hamas war news reports. The aforementioned framework served as the basis for identifying various frames employed by news writers in their articles. To expound, Semetko and Valkenburg's news frames consist of five classifications. These are conflict, human interest, attribution of responsibility, morality, and economic consequences. The first frame is the conflict frame which is used to show disagreements among individuals, groups, or organizations. In the study of Semetko and Valkenburg (2000), this frame was the second most common, and it was found that the more serious the newspaper, the more the conflict frame was in evidence. Secondly, the human-interest frame, the second mechanism which adds a human or emotional perspective to events. The attribution of responsibility frame, the third mechanism, assigns responsibility to the government, an individual, or a group. The morality frame, the fourth mechanism, puts events or issues in the context of morals, social norms, and religious beliefs. Journalists often use the morality frame indirectly through quotations or inference rather than directly because of the journalistic norm of objectivity. Lastly, the economic framework discusses the impact of a problem or issue on individuals, groups, societies, or countries.

Whereas, the second question was answered by the theoretical framework of Fairclough (1995) and Yule (2010) which is about the morphosemantic and syntactic features present in news articles. I read the contents of the corpora to initially identify potential features based on the theories of the mentioned authors. Afterward, I organized the data and wrote logical descriptions supported by data extracts to answer the qualitative research questions of this study and contextualized the analysis concerning the prevailing literature.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure proper practice and conduct of the study, the ethical codes were considered and followed which were observed and applied towards the implementation of this study. These were the following: respect for persons, beneficence, justice, consent, and confidentiality (Mac et al., 2005).

Respect for persons demands a dedication to upholding the autonomy of study participants and, if autonomy may be compromised, to shield them from being taken advantage of because of their vulnerability. All research subjects must be treated with dignity. Following this rule guarantees that individuals will not be employed only as a way to further research goals (Mac et al., 2005).

Since this study was corpora-based and did not involve interviewing research participants to collect data, this principle was upheld by ensuring that no individuals/writers included in the news articles that were used as research material was used for non-academic

purposes. The researcher ensured that the materials were used solely for educational and research purposes, with no intention of exploiting or misrepresenting the writers. The focus of the study remained academic and respectful throughout. Moreover, the researcher strictly adhered to ethical guidelines concerning the use of the data. All articles used for research purposes were selected and treated with utmost respect for the privacy and rights of the individuals featured in them. Personal information or identifying details of the authors were carefully anonymized or removed to protect their privacy. This practice helped maintain the confidentiality of the individuals involved and upheld their dignity.

Researchers must respect informed consent as a matter of ethics. According to Jefford and Moore (2008), the informed consent ethical principle is that the researcher guarantees or ensures that research participants participate in the study voluntarily and with full knowledge of what it takes to be a part of the research (Richards & Schwartz, 2002). Before starting the research, the researchers must make sure the participants have given their consent. Before the participant (potentially) enters the study, consent must be sought.

The corpora of this research were taken from the internet; hence, such were readily available, and consent was no longer required. When using publicly available corpora from the internet in research, consent from individuals who generated or shared that content may not be required due to the nature of publicly accessible information. However, ethical considerations for the proper handling and use of these materials ensure ethical conduct in handling the materials. The research adhered to ethical guidelines and codes of conduct relevant to academic research, particularly in cases involving internet-based data. These guidelines often emphasize the importance of respecting intellectual property rights and maintaining the confidentiality of individuals. Moreover, the researcher maintained robust data security practices to prevent unauthorized access to the research materials. This included secure storage, password protection, and encryption where necessary, to safeguard the integrity and confidentiality of the data.

Beneficence refers to moral behavior that involves acting in ways that are beneficial to others while encouraging their safety and welfare (Pieper & Thomson, 2016). In qualitative research, researchers must safeguard subjects from harm, defend their autonomy, and respect their welfare. Moral behavior known as beneficence is classified as acts of kindness and altruism that go above and beyond the call of duty (Arifin, 2018). Researchers can adhere to this code of ethics by avoiding harm, limiting harm, and maximizing any potential benefits.

The corpora utilized in this study were never used to harm, disrespect, or insult the persons featured in the materials. The researcher secured the protection and well-being of such individuals by safeguarding the utilization of the materials strictly for research use. On the other hand, the researcher guaranteed that the results of the analysis were of significant use for those individuals who are in the news and media industry. By framing the research in this way, the study aimed to benefit both researchers and society at large by advancing knowledge and understanding of the linguistic representation of news articles about the Israel and Hamas conflict. To maximize benefits and minimize harm, the researcher handled the data with care and sensitivity. This includes ensuring that potentially sensitive or harmful content were used and reported ethically, avoiding any potential harm to individuals or groups mentioned in the corpora. On the other hand, the study was conducted with a commitment to avoiding harm to news writers and media in general. It refrained from engaging in any activities that could negatively impact these communities and respected the norms and guidelines of the online platforms.

When conducting research, researchers should adhere to the ethical principles of maintaining confidentiality and privacy. The terms confidentiality and anonymity are frequently used interchangeably in human subject research, therefore recognizing the distinction between the two is essential when developing protocols to ensure ethical conduct in research. According to Kaiser (2009), confidentiality describes a scenario in which the researcher is aware of the participant's identity but takes the appropriate precautions to prevent that identity from being recognized or learned by others.

In the course of this corpora-based research, where no research participants were involved, maintaining confidentiality was paramount. Thus, the researcher implemented a series of measures to protect the privacy and rights of the writers whose publicly available online data were analyzed. Anonymization was achieved through the removal of personally identifiable information, ensuring that no names or identifying details were disclosed. Instead, codes and labels were adeptly used as substitutes for specific identifiers. Additionally, transparent reporting practices and secure data storage procedures further reinforced the commitment to safeguarding confidentiality. Thus, the research diligently adhered to pertinent legal and ethical standards concerning data privacy and confidentiality, guaranteeing full compliance with the prevailing regulations and guidelines.

Justice is characterized by the equitable treatment of every individual, ensuring that each person, irrespective of age, gender, race, religion, socioeconomic status, or other variables, is afforded an equal opportunity to partake in the advantages and costs of the research. Nevertheless, it is the ethical obligation of the researcher to ensure that their research does not lead to any form of injustice or bias at any phase of the study, particularly in the selection of research participants, to prevent the exclusion of any particular group (Farrugia, 2019).

To ensure justice in this study, the researcher established specific inclusion criteria when selecting corpora for analysis. These criteria were designed to be objective and non-discriminatory, ensuring that a diverse range of news articles were included, thus avoiding any undue exclusion or bias. The selection process for corpora followed a systematic and unbiased approach, offering equal opportunity to all eligible materials that meet the predefined criteria. This approach prevented favoritism or arbitrary selection, promoting fairness in

the research. Moreover, during the analysis phase, the researcher maintained an impartial stance when examining the framing techniques of news writers. The analysis aimed to be objective and free from any preconceived judgments or biases, ensuring that each writer's discourse received equitable scrutiny.

On the other hand, recognizing that the primary beneficiaries of this study would be the journalists themselves, the researcher emphasized the practical relevance of the research findings. The results were presented in a way that could be applied by journalists to enhance their techniques in framing their news articles, thereby promoting equitable access to research outcomes.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study. The presentation of the results followed the order of the research questions: Framing of the Israel-Hamas war news reports and the morphosemantic and syntactic features present in the news articles.

Research Question 1: What framing of the Israel-Hamas war news reports is evident in various news providers?

This part delves into the framing techniques evident in the Israel-Hamas war news reports. The analysis was based upon Semetko and Valkenburg's (2000) Five News Framing Techniques which are the attribution of responsibility, human interest frame, conflict frame, morality frame, and economic frame.

Table 1.1. *Conflict Frame in News Articles on Israel-Hamas War*

<i>News Framing Technique</i>	<i>News Article Excerpts</i>
Conflict Frame	"Israel's bombardment of Gaza is 'narrowing the window' for a new truce." -NA06 "The strike marks the first targeted assassination of a Hamas official outside Palestinian Territories" -NA09 "At least eight people were killed in an Israeli airstrike on buildings in central Gaza on Saturday afternoon local time" -NA15 "Israel's latest attacks on Gaza have killed at least 151 people" -NA10 "Israel has been bombarding Rafah with airstrikes for weeks and says it is committed to a ground offensive as the alternative..." -NA22

News Framing Technique in News Articles on Israel-Hamas War. After scrutinizing the corpora, this study revealed that among the five news framing techniques three framing techniques were prominent. These are the conflict frame, human interest frame, and attribution of responsibility. Table 1 unveiled that Conflict framing was prominently utilized in the news articles of the Israel-Hamas war. This particular framing technique involved disagreement among various parties, individuals, groups, or countries. In the analysis of the thirty (30) news articles conducted in this study, it was determined that out of the sixteen (16) samples examined, five (5) of the most exemplary articles effectively employed conflict frames. This indicates that media outlets highlight the war that ignited because of the dispute between Israel and Hamas. Some of them are the following:

"Israel's bombardment of Gaza is 'narrowing the window' for a new truce." (NA06)

"The strike marks the first targeted assassination of a Hamas official outside Palestinian Territories" (NA09)

"Israel's latest attacks on Gaza have killed at least 151 people" (NA10)

"At least eight people were killed in an Israeli airstrike on buildings in central Gaza on Saturday afternoon local time" (NA15)

"Israel has been bombarding Rafah with airstrikes for weeks and says it is committed to a ground offensive as the alternative..." (NA22)

The extracted excerpts from the samples underscore the prevalence of disagreement and conflict between the involved parties. The choice of words employed in the excerpts, such as bombardment, assassination, attacks, and killed/killing, directly correlated with the tense and confrontational nature of the situation. The excerpts demonstrate conflict framing methods by presenting Israel's actions as firm or forceful, while downplaying or providing context for the actions of Hamas or Palestinians. For example, statements such as "Israel's bombing of Gaza is 'closing the opportunity' for a new ceasefire" (NA06) and "The attack represents the initial deliberate killing of a Hamas leader outside Palestinian Territories" (NA09) emphasize Israel's active involvement in influencing the conflict's story.

Moreover, statements such as "Israel has caused the death of at least 151 individuals in Gaza" (NA10) and "A minimum of eight individuals lost their lives in a bombing by Israel on buildings in central Gaza on Saturday afternoon" (NA15) highlight the outcomes of Israeli actions, usually highlighting the fatalities or damage incurred, potentially presenting Israel as the one initiating conflict. Israel's actions in NA22 are response to a perceived threat or out of necessity. By claiming that Israel has been conducting airstrikes in Rafah "for weeks" and asserting that a ground offensive is the only alternative, it implies that Israel sees its military actions as necessary measures for defense. This framing method suggests that Israel is defending itself or reacting to provocation, possibly influencing how the reader sees the conflict and supporting Israel's military actions. In general, these samples show how language selections can shape views of the conflict by emphasizing specific actions, results, or individuals.

Table 1.2. Human Interest Framing in News Articles on Israel-Hamas War

News Framing Technique	Category	News Article Excerpts
Human Interest Frame	Human Example or human face	<p>“Women are unable to give birth safely and children cannot get vaccinated, with cases of infectious diseases on the rise and people seeking shelter in hospital yards.” -NA02</p> <p>“In the besieged strip, more than two million people are in need of food and the medical system has all but collapsed.” -NA11</p> <p>“On Thursday, US President Joe Biden announced that the US military would begin establishing a port in the territory...” -NA11</p> <p>“...fighter jets fired two air-to-surface missiles at a house in the Al-Ain area of Kharbet Selim, killing a man, his pregnant wife, their two children and another individual.” -NA13</p> <p>“People with evident signs of starvation stopping trucks in search of anything they can get to survive.” -NA02</p>
	Emphasis on the effect to the individuals or groups	<p>“...the lack of respect for the humanitarian notification system puts every movement of aid workers in danger.” -NA02</p> <p>“The New York Times published an investigation that uncovered new details showing a pattern of rape, mutilation and extreme brutality against women...” -NA04</p> <p>“82 people were killed over the past 24 hours, bringing the death toll in the Gaza Strip to 30,960 since October 7. A number of victims remained under rubble” -NA20</p> <p>“According to the figures, a total of 12,193 children were killed between 2019 and 2022 globally, and a total of 12,300 children were killed in Gaza between October 2023 and February 2024.” -NA28</p>
	Use of vignettes or adjectives To evoke emotions and feelings	<p>“...This is the dire picture of conditions in northern Gaza painted by a top UN official in charge of relief operations in the enclave.” -NA02</p> <p>“Colleagues who have managed to make it to the north in recent days describe scenes of utter horror: Corpses left lying in the road.” -NA02</p> <p>“US military would begin establishing a port in the territory that could receive large shipments of critically needed food and medical supplies, with Gaza in the grips of a harrowing humanitarian crisis.” -NA11</p> <p>“It comes as water, hygiene and sanitation services “remain severely constrained” in the war-torn strip” -NA19</p>
	Presentation of visual information that can lead to feelings	<p>“People starving and dead bodies left in the streets.” -NA02</p> <p>“The risk of famine grows by the day as food and water is running out.” -NA02</p> <p>“...people in Gaza drinking polluted water and facing unsanitary conditions, as starvation and dehydration increasingly become threats in the enclave.” -NA19</p> <p>“What we have seen since October 7 is a stain on our collective conscience. Unless we act, it will become an indelible mark on our humanity.” -NA02</p>
	Highlighting personal stories from involved actors	<p>“... Hamas said in a statement that the group’s leaders “categorically deny such allegations...” -NA04</p> <p>“We are lacking literally everything: We are lacking electricity, fuel, food, water — anything (for) our basic needs...” -NA15</p> <p>Hammash called for a permanent ceasefire to the war. “We don’t want to find ourselves in that circle of violence again and again,” he said. -NA16</p>

Human Interest Framing in News Articles on Israel-Hamas War. Table 1.2 shows that Human Interest framing was the second most recurring framing technique employed by media outlets on Israel-Hamas news articles. This type of framing brings a human face or an emotional angle to the presentation of an event, issue, or problem. This frame is employed in order to personalize the news, dramatize, or “emotionalize” the news, in order to capture and retain the interest of the audience. In the context of this study, after scrutinizing the corpora, seven articles out of 30 articles used the human-interest frame.

Utilizing the Semetko and Valkenburg’s (2000) News Framing Mechanism, the researcher classified into five categories which are the human example of human face; emphasis on the effect to the individuals or groups; use of vignettes or adjectives to evoke emotions and feelings; presentation of visual information that can lead to feelings; and highlighting personal stories from involved actors.

Human example or human face is a subcategory of the Human-Interest Frame which accentuate emotions to the news through the addition of human example or human face as a completing and triggering point for the people to read because generally, people are affective. This particular framing technique enhances emotional resonance and audience connection. Including a human face or human example act as a supplement and catalyst for readers which pulls them into the story and urges them to remain engaged. This strategy recognizes the inherent emotional aspect of people which play a part in influencing how news is perceived and reacted to. Samples under this subcategory are:

“Women are unable to give birth safely and children cannot get vaccinated, with cases of infectious diseases on the rise and people seeking shelter in hospital yards.” (NA02)

“In the besieged strip, more than two million people are in need of food and the medical system has all but collapsed.” (NA11)

“On Thursday, US President Joe Biden announced that the US military would begin establishing a port in the territory...” (NA11)

“...fighter jets fired two air-to-surface missiles at a house in the Al-Ain area of Kharbet Selim, killing a man, his pregnant wife, their two children and another individual.” (NA13)

News article 2 mentions Human examples or human faces which are women and children, along with news article 13. Bringing up women and children in news stories aims to trigger emotional reactions in readers by appealing to their empathy and compassion since women and children are commonly viewed as representations of innocence, purity, and care. Their involvement in the war evokes emotions of empathy and worry in those who read them. The deliberate use of women and children in news articles on the Israel-Hamas war is a powerful newswriting strategy that captures the attention of the readers and sparks empathy.

Notably, in the excerpts above, one mentioned two million people, one mentioned the US President Joe Biden and one mentioned a man, a wife, his pregnant wife, their two children, and an individual. These human faces/human examples were used in order to evoke emotion. In NA11, two million people are in need of food and medical assistance because of the war. Readers can perceive the said figure as something that is concerning, and therefore appealing to their emotions. NA11 also mentioned the US President Joe Biden which made an announcement regarding the significant intervention in response to the dire situation unfolding in Gaza. Mentioning the US President personalizes the intervention and portrays it as a direct action taken by a prominent political figure which enhances the significance and legitimacy in the eyes of the audience. Through linking the president’s name to the humanitarian initiative, it implies that it has garnered the attention and concern of the highest levels of government across the world.

On the other hand, NA13 mentioned a man, his pregnant wife, their two children, and an individual which are the primary victims that were killed after Israeli airstrikes in southern Lebanon. Mentioning them evokes empathy and emotional responses from the audience. This was framed to highlight the devastating consequences of the airstrikes and meant to invite readers to empathize with the pain and loss experienced by the affected family. This elicits a stronger emotional reaction and potentially mobilizes public opinion towards condemning such actions.

Next subcategory is the emphasis on the effect to the individuals or groups. The effects of the Israel-Hamas war vary across individuals or groups, and emphasizing them draws attention from the readers. This includes placing emphasis on the stories of individuals directly impacted by the violence, such as people suffering, groups of people being in danger, and many more. Framing news articles in this way contributes to humanizing the conflict, wherein the effects of the war on various sectors are mentioned to make it compelling for readers. Media outlets use this approach to prompt empathy towards the victims. Samples of news articles on the Israel-Hamas war emphasizing the effect on individuals or groups are as follows:

“People with evident signs of starvation stopping trucks in search of anything they can get to survive.” (NA02)

“...the lack of respect for the humanitarian notification system puts every movement of aid workers in danger.” (NA02)

“The New York Times published an investigation that uncovered new details showing a pattern of rape, mutilation and extreme brutality against women...” (NA04)

“82 people were killed over the past 24 hours, bringing the death toll in the Gaza Strip to 30,960 since October 7. A number of victims remained under rubble” (NA20)

“According to the figures, a total of 12,193 children were killed between 2019 and 2022 globally, and a total of 12,300 children were killed in Gaza between October 2023 and February 2024.” (NA28)

The excerpts all talk about the effects of the war on various people and groups who are victims of the violence. In NA02, the evident starvation of people who stop trucks in search of anything they can get to survive is deemed as one of the major effects of the war, having food scarcity. The most recurring emphasis of effects to individuals is the death toll and danger people face amidst the war. For example, NA02 focuses on the effects of the war to aid workers; NA04 discusses the patterns of rape, mutilation and extreme brutality against women; while NA20 and NA28 states the number of people killed. This implies that the consequences of the Israel-Hamas war extended far beyond mere statistics impacting individuals and communities in devastating ways. The excerpts above exemplify the emphasis of the effects which is a reminder of the human suffering caused by the conflict.

Thirdly, the use of vignettes or adjectives to evoke emotions and feelings is one of the five subcategories of human interest based on the theory of Semetko and Valkenburg (2000). Here, the emotional effects on the readers were also influenced by the war’s impact on the victims. The news articles of these events primarily aimed to evoke emotions rather than just report the news, in order to convey the true impact of the suffering and tragedy. The use of vignettes and powerful adjectives to depict the experiences and emotions of victims in human interest stories is discovered to greatly influence readers. People react more positively to emotions compared to facts.

“...This is the dire picture of conditions in northern Gaza painted by a top UN official in charge of relief operations in the enclave.” (NA02)

“Colleagues who have managed to make it to the north in recent days describe scenes of utter horror: Corpses left lying in the road.”

(NA02)

“US military would begin establishing a port in the territory that could receive large shipments of critically needed food and medical supplies, with Gaza in the grips of a harrowing humanitarian crisis.” (NA11)

“It comes as water, hygiene and sanitation services “remain severely constrained” in the war-torn strip” (NA19)

An excerpt from NA02 portrays a bleak image of the situation in northern Gaza, labeling it as “dire.” The term “dire” creates a feeling of urgency and seriousness which elicits concern and distress in the reader right away. Further, the use of the phrase “scenes of complete horror” in the second excerpt adds to the emotional intensity by presenting a disturbing and troubling depiction of bodies abandoned on the street. These glimpses of pain and hopelessness elicit strong emotional responses causing the reader to feel empathy for those impacted by the conflict in Gaza. NA11 excerpt underscores the seriousness of the humanitarian crisis in Gaza - referring to it as “harrowing.” This expresses deep suffering and pain and evokes sympathy and worry in readers. The usage of such emotive language is a call for desperate need for assistance and intervention in Gaza.

Lastly, the excerpt from NA19 talks about the challenges faced by the people of Gaza, particularly in relation to water, hygiene, and sanitation services. The phrase “remain severely constrained” conveys the ongoing hardship and struggle. This vignette of adversity pinpoints the impact of the conflict on the daily lives of individuals who are affected by the Israel-Hamas war. Through using descriptive language and emotive adjectives, the article captures the human dimension of the war which prompts the readers to engage emotionally with the experiences of those affected.

Subsequently, the presentation of visual information that can lead to feelings. Visual presentation in news articles about the Israel-Hamas conflict is a tool used by media outlets to present the situation in a way that allows readers to vividly imagine and understand the realities of the conflict through the use of words. This enhances the storytelling aspect of news articles, making complicated reportage more accessible to readers through presenting visual information that can lead to feelings. By presenting visual information that resonates with readers on an emotional level, news articles can evoke empathy, compassion, and a sense of urgency for addressing the humanitarian crisis. Examples of news articles that effectively employed visual presentation to convey the human dimension of the Israel-Hamas conflict include:

“People starving and dead bodies left in the streets.” (NA02)

“The risk of famine grows by the day as food and water is running out.” (NA02)

“...people in Gaza drinking polluted water and facing unsanitary conditions, as starvation and dehydration increasingly become threats in the enclave.” (NA19)

The excerpts above are examples from the corpora which utilize the presentation of visual information that can lead to feelings. NA02, conveys horror and despair which evokes feelings of shock, sorrow, and empathy in the reader. The visual imagery of starving individuals and bodies left unattended in the streets creates a visceral response which paints a picture to the dire humanitarian crisis and the consequences of the conflict on the civilian population. The second excerpt which is also from NA02, presents a visual presentation of the plight of those facing the threat of famine. This presents feelings of anxiety, desperation, and helplessness which connects to the readers for them to empathize with the victims. Whereas, NA19 presents the deteriorating living conditions and health risks faced by individuals in Gaza. This is pictured out people drinking polluted water and facing unsanitary conditions - one of the major effects of the Israel-Hamas conflict.

Lastly, highlighting personal stories from involved actors. This study reveals that media outlets in writing the articles on the Israel-Hamas war also employed the technique of highlighting personal stories from involved actors which serve as a supplement or a supporting statement to strengthen the appeal of the article towards the readers. Through spotlighting the personal narratives and experiences of those on the ground, media outlets evoke empathy from their readers and compel them to connect with the sufferings of the victims. The excerpts below are the samples extracted from the corpora:

“What we have seen since October 7 is a stain on our collective conscience. Unless we act, it will become an indelible mark on our humanity.” (NA02)

“...Hamas said in a statement that the group’s leaders “categorically deny such allegations...” (NA04)

“We are lacking literally everything: We are lacking electricity, fuel, food, water — anything (for) our basic needs,” (NA15)

Hammash called for a permanent ceasefire to the war. “We don’t want to find ourselves in that circle of violence again and again,” he said. (NA16)

These excerpts are parts of the news articles that the researcher scrutinized in this study. NA02 appears to be a statement made by the UN Under-Secretary-General for Humanitarian Affairs and Emergency Relief Coordinator who criticized Israel’s actions particularly denying critical supplies to northern Gaza and issuing evacuation orders which resulted in increased civilian suffering. Griffiths acknowledges the impact of Hamas’ attacks on Israel but underscored the urgency of addressing the situation in Gaza to prevent further humanitarian catastrophe. Through including such statements, news writers aim to convey the moral urgency and emotional weight of

the situation which draws readers’ attention to the humanitarian aspect of the conflict.

In news article 4, the news writer included a direct quote from a Hamas spokesperson which offers the perspective of one of the key actors involved in the conflict. Through incorporating the voice of Hamas, the article provides a more comprehensive and balanced view of the situation and allows the readers to understand the motivation and responses of different parties involved. This narrative, albeit from an militant group standpoint, adds depth to the coverage. NA15 features the first-hand account of an individual directly affected by the conflict who happens to be a civilian residing in the affected area of the war. Adding this personal narrative provides a glimpse of the experience of the victim therefore offering another aspect of the conflict. While NA16 stipulated the statement from Yousef Hammash, a Gaza resident and advocacy officer for the Norwegian Refugee Council who stated his call for a permanent ceasefire to the war which shows the desires and aspirations of individuals directly impacted by the conflict. Adding this statement appeals to the emotions of the readers on an emotional level because it shows the inherent destructive nature of war and emphasizes its pervasive lack of positive outcomes.

Table 1.3. *Responsibility Framing Technique in News Articles on Israel-Hamas War*

<i>Framing Technique</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>News Article Excerpts</i>
Responsibility Frame	Responsibility Allocating the Blame	“Hamas said in a statement that the group’s leaders “categorically deny such allegations” and called them a part of Israel’s attempt to justify the killing of Palestinian civilians.” -NA04 “Israel may have broken international law in Gaza, Lord Cameron has said...” -NA07 “The IDF said Mustafa was responsible for “Hamas’ international terrorist activities, directing terrorist cells and activities in the field, and advancing terror attacks against Israeli and Jewish targets in various countries around the world.” -NA29 “The U.N. agency for Palestinian refugees said in a statement Wednesday that at least one of its staff members was killed and 22 were injured when Israeli forces struck one of its food distribution centers in southern Gaza.” -NA30
	Societal Solutions	“...the US military would begin establishing a port in the territory that could receive large shipments of critically needed food and medical supplies.” -NA11 “The Jordanian Armed Forces made 10 airdrops of humanitarian relief into northern Gaza on Saturday.” -NA12 “Jordan continues its endeavors and efforts to send more medical, relief and food aid to people in the Gaza Strip with the aim of compensating for the acute shortage of food and medicine as a result of the continuing Israeli war on the Strip.” -NA12

Responsibility Framing Technique in News Articles on Israel-Hamas War. After a thorough analysis of data taken from news articles on the Israel-Hamas war, the study identified the third most recurring framing technique employed which is the responsibility frame. The responsibility framing technique in news articles involves the presentation of information in a way that pinpoints who or what is accountable for certain events, actions, or consequences. This particular technique aims to clarify the roles and obligations of individuals or groups involved in a particular situation. Through framing news stories through the lens of responsibility, journalists seek to inform the public about the actions of relevant stakeholders which highlights accountability. This frame has two subcategories which are the responsibility of allocating the blame and societal solutions. In this study, six news articles employed the responsibility frame.

The first subcategory under responsibility framing is the responsibility of allocating the blame. This subcategory of the responsibility frame refers to the presentation of information in a way that highlights who or what is accountable for certain events, actions, or consequences. This aims to clarify the roles and obligations of individuals, groups, or institutions involved in a particular situation. Through framing news articles through the lens of responsibility, journalists seek to inform the public about the actions of relevant stakeholders, and potentially influence public opinion, thereby promoting accountability. In context, excerpts from the news articles on Israel-Hamas war that employed the responsibility of allocating the blame are as follows:

“Hamas said in a statement that the group’s leaders “categorically deny such allegations” and called them a part of Israel’s attempt to justify the killing of Palestinian civilians.” (NA04)

“Israel may have broken international law in Gaza, Lord Cameron has said...” (NA07)

“The IDF said Mustafa was responsible for “Hamas’ international terrorist activities, directing terrorist cells and activities in the field, and advancing terror attacks against Israeli and Jewish targets in various countries around the world.” (NA29)

“The U.N. agency for Palestinian refugees said in a statement Wednesday that at least one of its staff members was killed and 22 were injured when Israeli forces struck one of its food distribution centers in southern Gaza.” (NA30)

In news article 4, the frame allocates the allegations of sex crimes towards Hamas militant group. However, in the excerpt above, Hamas denies allegations made against them and called The United Nations as part of Israel’s attempt to justify the killing of Palestinian civilians. Therefore, there is an allocation of the blame regarding the issue and the journalist who wrote NA04 clarified it comprehensively. In NA07, this features Foreign Secretary Lord Cameron who pinpointed that Israel may have broken international

law in Gaza because particular premises have been bombed which is against the international law. NA07 is framed in a way that it puts emphasis on Israel who may have broken an international law.

In news article 29, on the other hand, the article puts the blame on Hamas operative Hadli Ali Mustafa who is said to be responsible for ‘Hamas’ international terrorist activities, directing terrorist cells and activities in the field and advancing terror attacks against Israeli and Jewish targets in various countries around the world. Lastly, NA30 talks about Israel being responsible for the killing of a staff member of the U.N. agency for Palestinian refugees and injuring 22 individuals in one of the distribution centers located in southern Gaza.

Second subcategory is societal solutions. This refers to the ways in which journalists in news articles present solutions to societal problems. Instead of just focusing on problems or conflicts, journalists also have an important responsibility in bringing attention to possible solutions or actions that can solve these issues. In this specific category, reporters concentrate on suggesting realistic and achievable steps that individuals, communities, governments, or institutions can implement to address societal issues efficiently. Examples extracted from the corpora are the following:

“...the US military would begin establishing a port in the territory that could receive large shipments of critically needed food and medical supplies.” (NA11)

“The Jordanian Armed Forces made 10 airdrops of humanitarian relief into northern Gaza on Saturday.” (NA12)

"Jordan continues its endeavors and efforts to send more medical, relief and food aid to people in the Gaza Strip with the aim of compensating for the acute shortage of food and medicine as a result of the continuing Israeli war on the Strip." (NA12)

These articles showcase how journalism focuses on addressing the humanitarian crisis in Gaza caused by the conflict through societal solutions. In NA11, the US military's initiative to set up a port in the area for delivering significant amounts of food and medical supplies in the initial article shows a proactive stance towards offering necessary assistance to those requiring it. News article 12, the Jordanian Armed Forces' humanitarian assistance activities was highlighted, particularly by delivering relief supplies via airdrops to northern Gaza. This step highlights how crucial global aid and unity are in meeting the pressing needs of the impacted community. Additionally, the third excerpt which is also from NA12 highlights Jordan's continuous dedication to providing medical, relief, and food assistance to Gaza in order to address the critical lack of necessary resources caused by the conflict. By covering these projects, reporters not only bring attention to the humanitarian crisis but also showcase practical solutions and efforts that help alleviate the situation and assist impacted groups.

Research Question 2: What are the morphosemantic and syntactic features present in the news articles?

This particular part delves into the morphosemantic and syntactic features present in news articles on the Israel-Hamas war.

Morphosemantic Features of News Articles on Israel-Hamas War

Morphosemantic features are linguistic elements that bridge the realms of morphology and semantics. It focuses on the relationship between the structure and meaning of words. Unlike morphosyntactic features, which are determined by syntax and involve agreement or government, morphosemantic features are inherent characteristics that do not rely on syntactic rules for their expression. These features are marked on elements within a phrase or clause and can be present multiple times. Morphosemantic characteristics offer an insight into the formation of words and the interconnectedness of their meanings with their morphological makeup. By analyzing these characteristics, researchers can explore the processes that support language understanding, thinking, and interaction. This investigation improves understanding of how words are created and the structure of vocabulary, while also revealing the relationships between form and meaning.

Journalists who report on disasters strategically select their words and structure them for increased readership. This study discovered that the 30 news articles on Israel-Hamas war include linguistic elements such as Naming and referencing, rhetorical devices, figures of speech, emotional lexis, phrasal verbs, nominalization, passivity, and transitivity which are all presented in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1. *The Morphosemantic Features of News Articles on Israel-Hamas War*

<i>Morphosemantic Features</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Sample Statement from the Corpora</i>
Name and Referencing	Naming the Conflict/War	“Up to 1.9 million people, representing 85% of the population in Gaza, have been displaced, some multiple times, since the conflict began.” -NA02
		“Combat was also reported in urban refugee camps in central Gaza, where Israel expanded its offensive last week.” -NA08
		“The Houthis are among several Iranian proxy groups at the center of global concerns that the war in Gaza could spill further through the Mideast.” -NA18
Naming the Victim	According to Age	“Weiss’ daughter, 18; and wife, 53; were held in captivity in Gaza and released on Nov. 25 during a weeklong cease-fire.” -NA08
		“A 12-year-old Palestinian boy was shot and killed by a border police officer in Shuafat refugee camp in occupied east Jerusalem...” -NA21

Rhetorical Expressions	According to Status	<p>“Residents and the telecommunications company said Friday's fighting cut communications across Gaza.” -NA10</p> <p>“NNA reported that fighter jets fired two air-to-surface missiles at a house in the Al-Ain area of Kharbet Selim, killing a man, his pregnant wife, their two children and another individual.” -NA13</p> <p>“...an Israeli-American hostage was killed on October 7.” -NA26</p> <p>“More children were killed during four months of war in Gaza than in four years of conflict worldwide.” -NA28</p> <p>“At least five people were killed and 9 others injured in Israeli airstrikes in southern Lebanon on Saturday.” -NA13</p>
	According to Number	<p>“The number of people who have died of dehydration and malnutrition in Gaza has risen to at least 23” -NA19</p> <p>“The Gaza Ministry of Health said Saturday that 82 people were killed over the past 24 hours, bringing the death toll in the Gaza Strip to 30,960 since October 7.” -NA20</p> <p>“Twenty-four Israeli soldiers were killed during fighting in Gaza on Monday.” -NA23</p> <p>“Israeli forces have killed at least 433 Palestinians in the occupied West Bank.” -NA25</p>
	According to Situations during the War	<p>“Internally displaced families are sheltering in unsanitary, crowded conditions.” (NA19)</p> <p>“Panic is soaring in Rafah as desperate Palestinians decide whether to flee the last refuge in Gaza.” -NA22</p>
	Metonymy	<p>“Germany acknowledges diverging views in the international community on Israel’s military operation in Gaza.” (NA01)</p> <p>“The Foreign Secretary said he had seen things regarding the conflict that have been “deeply concerning” and called on Israel to restore water supply to Gaza.” -NA07</p> <p>“Four out of every five households in Gaza are without safe water, the United Nations warned Saturday.” -NA19</p>
	Personification	<p>“Germany expresses its rejection of the accusation of genocide brought against Israel.” -NA01</p> <p>“The war is in full swing.” -NA06</p> <p>“Israel said it could not comment without more specifics.” -NA10</p>
	Emotional Lexis	<p>“South Africa on Thursday had alleged Israel’s leadership was “intent on destroying the Palestinians as a group in Gaza...” -NA01</p> <p>“Aid workers are urging the US to pressure its ally Israel to lift the tight siege it holds on the enclave, which has left Palestinians on the brink of famine.” -NA12</p> <p>“A 12-year-old Palestinian boy was shot and killed by a border police officer in Shuafat refugee camp in occupied east Jerusalem.” -NA21</p>
	Phrasal Verbs	<p>“In response to the Times investigation, Hamas said in a statement that the group’s leaders “categorically deny such allegations” -NA04</p> <p>“The airdrops were carried out in cooperation with the United States, France, Egypt and Belgium, the military said in a statement.” -NA12</p> <p>“Panic is soaring in Rafah as desperate Palestinians decide whether to flee the last refuge in Gaza as Israel draws up plans for a ground offensive that the United Nations...” -NA22</p>
	Nominalization	<p>“Jordan continues its endeavors and efforts to send more medical, relief and food aid to people in the Gaza Strip...” -NA12</p> <p>The shooting came on the third night of the holy Muslim month of Ramadan, which has been a flashpoint in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict in previous years.” -NA21</p> <p>“That attack, which Hagari said happened several hundred meters from the eastern border, was the deadliest single incident for the IDF in Gaza since the ground invasion began on October 27.” -NA23</p>

This study reveals that the Israel-Hamas war was given names and references by the different journalists from various media outlets. Below are the names used by the journalists in referring to the war.

“Up to 1.9 million people, representing 85% of the population in Gaza, have been displaced, some multiple times, since the conflict began.” (NA02)

“Combat was also reported in urban refugee camps in central Gaza, where Israel expanded its offensive last week.” (NA08)

“The Houthis are among several Iranian proxy groups at the center of global concerns that the war in Gaza could spill further through the Mideast.” (NA18)

Analyzing articles from multiple news articles reveals the various naming methods used by writers. Journalists prefer to use different terms or parts of words to describe the war instead of using direct terms like "war" or "Israel-Hamas war." In News Article 2, the writer uses the term "conflict" as a representation. Likewise, news article 8 skillfully integrates the term "combat" into the story. Moreover, in article 18 of the news, the author chooses to use the phrase "the conflict in Gaza" to summarize the larger situation. This strategy enhances the reporting's depth and highlights how language can effectively convey the Israel-Hamas war without using the “war”

repetitively.

News articles that talked about the war have never failed to mention about the effect of it on people such as killings, abduction, damaged properties, and many more.

In highlighting these effects, journalists have their own ways of naming the victims of the war. Below are the excerpts from the news articles which illustrate that victims are named according to their respective age.

“His daughter, 18; and wife, 53; were held in captivity in Gaza and released on Nov. 25 during a weeklong cease-fire.” (NA08)

“A 12-year-old Palestinian boy was shot and killed by a border police officer in Shuafat refugee camp in occupied east Jerusalem...” (NA21)

In the excerpts mentioned, news writers used the victims' age to identify them. Actual identities were kept confidential, but using specific details about the victims, such as 18, 53, and 12-year-olds had a significant impact. Using the age of victims to elicit emotions from readers is effective, as children and elderly individuals involved in disasters can deeply resonate with parents and others.

In addition to using victims' age, reporters included the victims' status as well to enhance the impact of their news stories. As defined, status refers to the relative social, professional, or other standing of someone or something. In the news reports about the Israel-Hamas war, journalists chose to identify the victims by their roles or occupations rather than by their actual names. This method of including the victims enhances the news article as simply stating their names may not establish a personal connection for readers. Refer to the excerpts from the corpora below:

“Residents and the telecommunications company said Friday's fighting cut communications across Gaza.” (NA10)

“NNA reported that fighter jets fired two air-to-surface missiles at a house in the Al-Ain area of Kharbet Selim, killing a man, his pregnant wife, their two children and another individual.” (NA13)

“...an Israeli-American hostage was killed on October 7.” (NA26)

“More children were killed during four months of war in Gaza than in four years of conflict worldwide.” (NA28)

It was noted that the victims were named using a general term instead of their specific names. Journalists choose to utilize the status of individuals such as the term residents, a man, pregnant wife, children, or simply mentioning the term individual. Journalists choose to include labels indicating the victims' status in order to appeal to readers from the same community, as these labels represent different sectors of society and evoke empathy for the victims. Therefore, the news becomes more valuable.

It is also observed that in conflicts such as war, many individuals are eager to find out the number of casualties, injuries, and affected individuals. Journalists focus on the quantity of individuals impacted and incorporate that specific number when identifying the victims. Selections from the news articles demonstrate this:

“At least five people were killed and 9 others injured in Israeli airstrikes in southern Lebanon on Saturday.” (NA13)

“The number of people who have died of dehydration and malnutrition in Gaza has risen to at least 23” (NA19)

“The Gaza Ministry of Health said Saturday that 82 people were killed over the past 24 hours, bringing the death toll in the Gaza Strip to 30,960 since October 7.” (NA20)

“Twenty-four Israeli soldiers were killed during fighting in Gaza on Monday.” (NA23)

“Israeli forces have killed at least 433 Palestinians in the occupied West Bank.” (NA25)

Even with the specific numerical data provided as a reference to the victims, as seen in the examples above, the extent of the war was significant. There were an excessive number of individuals impacted and properties that suffered damage. Journalists approximate the number of victims when reporting. News stories about earthquakes often use language indicating approximation, such as the following:

“At least five people were killed and 9 others injured in Israeli airstrikes in southern Lebanon on Saturday.” (NA13)

“The number of people who have died of dehydration and malnutrition in Gaza has risen to at least 23” (NA19)

“Israeli forces have killed at least 433 Palestinians in the occupied West Bank.” (NA25)

Some news articles failed to provide the precise number of people impacted during the war, as demonstrated in the excerpt above. Journalists use words like at least, some, more, and nearly to indicate uncertainty about the number of victims while also assuring readers that the numbers are approximate in their articles. Because the war impacted the whole community, journalists cannot tally exact numbers but can provide estimates to represent the total number of victims.

A notable aspect in the naming and referencing of the war victims is that journalists opt to describe them using adjectives instead of mentioning their names.

“Internally displaced families are sheltering in unsanitary, crowded conditions.” (NA19)

“Panic is soaring in Rafah as desperate Palestinians decide whether to flee the last refuge in Gaza.” (NA22)

The adjectives that the journalists use reflect the situations of the victims. For example, the excerpt from news article 19 which mentions internally displaced families are sheltering in unsanitary, crowded conditions, the adjective displaced was carried out because as one of the results of the ongoing war, a lot of people were displaced or evacuated because their respective homes are no longer safe. Also, excerpt from news article 22 used the adjective desperate to describe the Palestinians who are victims also of the conflict. The usage of adjectives in naming the victims of the war is one strategy used by journalists to add impact to the subject of the article.

Also, News articles on the Israel-Hamas war are found to be rich in rhetorical expressions. Among these devices that are used are metonymy and personification. Metonymy refers to the practice of substituting the name of an attribute or adjunct for the intended subject. In essence, it involves using words that symbolize broader concepts, with these words serving as components within a larger framework. News articles frequently employ metonymy for several purposes, including enhancing conciseness by condensing multi-word concepts into single-word representations. This streamlined approach not only facilitates practicality in news writing but also enhances the article's appeal through the selection of evocative language.

The current study demonstrates that news articles discussing the Israel-Hamas war frequently employ metonymy to encapsulate a concept within a single frame, serving as a representative of a larger idea. This practice is exemplified by the following excerpts extracted from the corpora:

“Germany acknowledges diverging views in the international community on Israel’s military operation in Gaza.” (NA01)

“The Foreign Secretary said he had seen things regarding the conflict that have been “deeply concerning” and called on Israel to restore water supply to Gaza.” (NA07)

“Four out of every five households in Gaza are without safe water, the United Nations warned Saturday.” (NA19)

The emphasized terms mentioned above serve as deliberate choices made by journalists to symbolize the intended meanings, effectively representing the original expressions. Metonymy, a form of substitution where something associated with a concept is substituted for the concept itself, is frequently employed in news article composition. This practice often involves condensing lengthy expressions into single words or phrases that encapsulate their essence. Such strategic writing techniques enable journalists to craft concise and attention-grabbing expressions.

The terms "Germany," "Israel," and "United Nations" were used in news articles 1, 7, and 19 as examples of metonymy. This is due to the fact that these terms symbolize bigger entities or ideas connected to them. For example, "Germany" could represent the German government or its strategies, "Israel" could symbolize the Israeli government or its behavior, and "United Nations" could indicate the joint choices or resolutions made by the organization. These metonymic usages simplify complicated ideas into individual terms, improving clarity and conciseness in news coverage.

The 30 news articles discussing the Israel-Hamas war employed vivid language to depict the unfolding events. Adhering to the principles of news writing, which prioritize conciseness, clarity, and objectivity, these articles are akin to any other news pieces. Journalists infuse these reports with heightened intensity and drama, aiming to vividly convey the gravity of the situation and enable readers to fully visualize the unfolding events. In particular, personification emerges as a prominent characteristic of the news articles examined in this research. By attributing human-like qualities to the subjects discussed in the articles, emphasis is effectively heightened. The analysis of this study reveals that journalists skillfully manipulate language to evoke associations with diverse entities involved in the conflict. The following excerpts are the examples:

“Germany expresses its rejection of the accusation of genocide brought against Israel.” (NA01)

“The war is in full swing.” (NA06)

“Israel said it could not comment without more specifics.” (NA10)

The excerpt from NA01, is categorized as personification as it gives human-like characteristics, like expressing opinions and emotions, to Germany. Suggesting that Germany "expresses its rejection" implies that as a nation-state, Germany has the ability to think, speak, and act like individuals do. Countries do not have the ability to voice opinions or emotions; instead, it is the representatives or officials of the country who speak on behalf of the government or state. Thus, utilizing "expresses" in this scenario gives Germany human-like qualities, attributing to it the ability to articulate its perspective.

Similarly, NA10 also demonstrates personification by giving human-like communication abilities to Israel. When it is said, "Israel said," it implies that Israel, as a whole, has the ability to communicate and react. Yet in actuality, countries are unable to communicate or give declarations; instead, it is individuals acting as representatives or speaking for the country who do so. Hence, the use of "said" in this situation gives Israel human characteristics, making it seem capable of speaking.

Excerpt extracted from NA06 is also an example of personification as it gives human characteristics to the abstract idea of war. By

saying that "the war is in full swing," the sentence implies that war, a complicated and abstract concept, is actively involved in a physical activity similar to a human action. The expression "in full swing" signifies a period of intense movement or activity, often seen in activities like dancing or sports that involve humans. Nevertheless, war is not a living creature able to physically move or take action. Instead, it is a notion created by humans that is marked by disagreement and aggression. As a result, war is personified in this passage by being described as being "in full swing," giving it human-like characteristics and portraying it as actively involved in the events being depicted.

Syntactic Analysis of News Articles on Israel-Hamas war

Aside from analyzing the morphosemantic features of news articles on the Israel-Hamas war, the researcher also found the need to focus on the syntax of the news articles, as understanding how the sentences are constructed would also lead to a better and clearer understanding of the ideologies of the news writers, especially in framing their news stories related to the war.

The articles used in the study commonly used active voice in the sentences. However, there is also a very noticeable application of passive voice in the news articles, which are seen to reveal the writers’ imprint on their bias, agenda, or certain ideologies.

The use of active and passive sentences makes it impossible to report the events in a neutral way because these “choices, which the language system both enables and forces one to make in every utterance, are precisely the points at which the operation of ideology can and does occur.” Therefore, journalists have to make a choice whether to use active or passive sentences in delivering the news.

The meticulous analysis of the corpora used in this study leads to findings that commonly, news articles on disasters have a dominant usage of an active voice in the sentence. In the presentation of ideas and events, writers still make use of the basic active sentences. However, the researcher also acknowledged the journalists’ options of writing the sentences using the passive voice.

If sentences in the articles written in active form emphasized who did what and who said so, sentences in passive form focused more on what had been done. These sentences are important in reporting disaster news since people have to be informed about the event and to the event that transpired.

Passive sentences may either retain or drop the agent/actor responsible in carrying out the action denoted by the verb; but still, the emphasis of the sentence is on the action carried out. In the examples below, it can be noticed that the sentences using passive voice keep the agent or the actor of the sentences:

Passive Construction in News Articles on Israel-Hamas War. The use of passive sentences in news articles is not generally preferred, as active voice is considered more direct, concise, and engaging. However, there are specific instances where passive voice is more appropriate, such as the object is more important or newsworthy than the subject, or when the subject is unknown or unimportant. Passive voice can also be used strategically to evade accountability or to emphasize certain aspects of a story.

After a thorough analysis of the corpora, the study revealed that passive construction is present. Table 2.2 shows the samples which exemplifies passive construction in News Articles on Israel-Hamas war.

Table 2.2. *Passive Construction in News Articles on Israel-Hamas War*

<i>Example</i>	<i>Agent/Actor</i>	
	<i>Agent Specified</i>	<i>Agentless</i>
“The aftermath has been revealed by the residents.” -NA10	✓	
“The bodies were recovered and transported to the government hospital.” -NA13		✓
Passive voice is used to highlight the experiences of the victims		
“Evacuation of civilians had been carried out.” -NA02		✓
“2.3 million homes have been forcibly abandoned by the residents.” -NA05	✓	
Passive voice is used to illustrate death		
“23,708 people had been killed and more than 60,000 wounded by Israel's offensive, mostly civilians.” -NA10	✓	

Passive sentences can include or exclude the agent/actor who performs the action indicated by the verb, yet the main focus remains on the action itself. In the first two examples in the table, it is observed that sentences in passive voice may either include (NA10) or exclude (NA13) the agent or actor of the sentences. Also, two purposes of passive voice were identified, these are to highlight the experiences of the victims and to illustrate death. Firstly, to highlight the experiences of the victims, journalists focus on what was experienced by the victims. The following are examples:

“Evacuation of civilians had been carried out.” (NA02)

“2.3 million homes have been forcibly abandoned by the residents.” (NA05)

The excerpts above illustrate the usage of passive sentences to highlight the experiences of the victims. Excerpts stipulated above which are from news articles 2 and 5 are considered to be in the passive voice as they highlight the action being done to the subject instead of the subject carrying out the action. "Evacuation of civilians" is the subject in the first sentence but instead of performing the action of

evacuating, it is the one being evacuated. Likewise, in NA05, the subject is "2.3 million homes,"

which are not willingly abandoning themselves; rather, they are being left by someone else, presumably the residents. This passive construction focuses on the victims' experiences by highlighting the actions that were done to them instead of their own involvement in those actions. On the other hand, sentences are also written in passive voice to illustrate death, such as the examples below:

"23,708 people had been killed and more than 60,000 wounded by Israel's offensive, mostly civilians. (NA10)

The excerpts demonstrate the use of passive voice to showcase death by redirecting attention to the victims and the actions done to them instead of highlighting the perpetrators. In the excerpt from NA10, the focus is on the 23,708 individuals who were killed because of Israel's offensive, using a passive construction. The emphasis on the victims of the violence is brought out using passive voice, redirecting focus from the entity responsible for the killings to the human cost of the conflict.

Transitivity in News Articles on Israel-Hamas War. To complete the linguistic analysis of the corpora, this part of the paper presents the transitivity analysis of the news articles on the Israel-Hamas war. Transitivity is the range of choices available to a speaker when they express their perception of actions in the outside world and their own thoughts. This entails describing these procedures, along with the individuals and situations connected to them. Transitivity covers different kinds of processes, such as material, mental, relational, verbal, behavioral, and existential processes. In reporting on the Israel-Hamas conflict, journalists use transitivity to describe the ongoing events, perspectives, and complexities related to the conflict.

After scrutinizing the corpora, the study reveals that 30 out of 30 news articles use various verb processes. Table 2.3 presents the transitivity in news articles on the Israel-Hamas war.

Table 2.3. *Transitivity in News Articles on Israel-Hamas War*

<i>Verb Processes</i>	<i>Sample Statement</i>
Material Process	"Rocket fire continues to pound populated areas of Israel." -NA02
	"Jordan said it has carried out 35 aid airdrops on Gaza since November 6." -NA12
	"Israel has been bombarding Rafah with airstrikes for weeks and says it is committed to a ground offensive." -NA22
Relational Process	"...the war is in full swing..." NA06
	"Arouri was deputy head of Hamas's politburo and a founder of its military wing, the Qassam Brigades." -NA09
	"The Houthis are among several Iranian proxy groups at the center of global concerns that the war in Gaza could spill further through the Mideast." -NA18
Verbal Processes	"The Foreign Secretary said he had seen things regarding the conflict that have been "deeply concerning" and called on Israel to restore water supply to Gaza." -NA07
	"Netanyahu has vowed to press ahead with the military offensive until Hamas is crushed." -NA08
	"The UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs said 15 Israelis, including four members of the Israeli forces, have been killed and 99 wounded in the West Bank." -NA25
Behavioral Process	"Israel on Friday rejected what it called the "grossly distorted" accusation of genocide leveled against it by South Africa." -NA01
	"He declined to be drawn on whether the deprivation of water to the civilian population breached international humanitarian law." -NA07
	"Several people gather around him, while a woman screams and calls his name." -NA21
Mental Processes	"Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu is under significant pressure to do whatever is required to get the remaining hostages who are still alive." -NA03
	"Tzafir believes the world should see that Hamas must be defeated so it is no longer a threat." -NA05
	"Biden is eager to revisit Israel and deliver a speech before the country's parliament." -NA14
Existential Process	"...there is wide support among Palestinians for Hamas's deadly attacks on Israel which triggered it." -NA05
	"There has been daily cross-border fire between Israel and Lebanon since the war in Gaza began. -NA13 "There are casualties among the Israeli forces who dispersed the demonstrators at the Shuafat camp" -NA21

Material processes in transitivity refer to physical actions like reading, writing, running, etc. They convey the idea that a certain entity "performs" an action, which can be directed towards another entity. News articles on the Israel-Hamas conflict use material processes to depict the physical actions carried out by the involved actors. Samples extracted from the corpora are the following:

"Rocket fire continues to pound populated areas of Israel." (NA02)

"Jordan said it has carried out 35 aid airdrops on Gaza since November 6." (NA12)

"Israel has been bombarding Rafah with airstrikes for weeks and says it is committed to a ground offensive." (NA22)

These selections demonstrate material processes in transitivity by portraying physical actions or events that can be directly seen or quantified. In NA02, rocket fire is still striking populated areas of Israel in the first excerpt, causing physical harm to the regions. Likewise, in the NA12, "Jordan reported conducting 35 aid airdrops in Gaza," the process of performing aid airdrops includes physically delivering aid items from airplanes to the designated area in Gaza. Lastly, in NA22, "Israel has been attacking Rafah with airstrikes," the act of attacking Rafah with airstrikes involves the actual action of carrying out airstrikes on the city of Rafah. These material

processes under transitivity aid in showing the continuous actions and progression in the Israel-Hamas conflict. The relational process is also evident in the news articles. This is employed by journalists to depict abstract relationships between entities like existence, possession, and transformation. See samples below:

“...the war is (RELATIONAL) in full swing...” (NA06)

“Arouri was (RELATIONAL) deputy head of Hamas's politburo and a founder of its military wing, the Qassam Brigades.” (NA09)

“The Houthis are (RELATIONAL) among several Iranian proxy groups at the center of global concerns that the war in Gaza could spill further through the Mideast.” (NA18)

These selected excerpts illustrate relational processes within transitivity by showing connections between entities or ideas. In NA06, when it says “the war is in full swing,” it means that the war is currently happening at its highest intensity or activity level. In NA09, the mention of “Arouri serving as deputy head of Hamas's politburo” illustrates Arouri's role in the organization, indicating his place in Hamas's leadership hierarchy. In NA18, “The Houthis are one of multiple Iranian-aligned groups,” the statement “one of multiple Iranian-aligned groups” emphasizes the connection between the Houthis and other groups backed by Iran, placing them in a wider framework of regional partnerships. These relational processes assist in illustrating the interconnections and functions of different entities in the Israel-Hamas conflict context.

The next process that is evident in the corpora is the verbal processes which describe verbal actions, such as speaking, explaining, or stating. They are very similar to material action processes, but they describe a verbal action instead of a physical action. See examples below:

“The Foreign Secretary said he had seen things regarding the conflict that have been “deeply concerning” and called on Israel to restore water supply to Gaza.” (NA07)

“Netanyahu has vowed to press ahead with the military offensive until Hamas is crushed.” (NA08)

“The UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs said 15 Israelis, including four members of the Israeli forces, have been killed and 99 wounded in the West Bank.” (NA25)

These passages demonstrate how verbal processes in transitivity consist of actions or processes that are communicated through verbs. In every case, there is an action taking place or being explained. In the passage about the Foreign Secretary's statement (NA07), the act of speaking or communicating is indicated by the verb “said.” This process of speaking involves communicating information or addressing issues. Also, Netanyahu's commitment to continue with the military attack is shown in NA08 through the use of the word “vowed,” which signifies a pledge or dedication. This spoken statement emphasizes his resolve to keep up the attack. In NA25, the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs is described as sharing details about casualties in the West Bank using the word “said.” This process of speaking includes the action of sharing or communicating information. These verbal processes examples demonstrate actions, statements, or expressions carried out by individuals or organizations participating in the events that are being discussed.

Next, the behavioral process under transitivity. This refers to processes that describe the behavior of an entity, such as laughing, crying, or sleeping. In the corpora investigated in this present study, behavioral processes are evident. The following excerpts exemplifies behavioral processes:

“Israel on Friday rejected what it called the “grossly distorted” accusation of genocide leveled against it by South Africa.” (NA01)

“He declined to be drawn on whether the deprivation of water to the civilian population breached international humanitarian law.” (NA07)

“Several people gather around him, while a woman screams and calls his name.” (NA21)

The examples above demonstrate how transitivity operates through actions carried out by individuals or entities. In NA01, Israel's denial of committing genocide is based on how they respond behaviorally to the accusation. The term “rejected” describes an act of declining or resisting. Likewise, in NA07, the person's choice to not answer about the lack of water involves a decision about their behavior, as indicated by the word “declined.” This choice signifies a purposeful decision to refrain from participating in a specific behavior. In the third excerpt (NA21), multiple individuals come together around the person as a woman shouts and calls out his name, demonstrating how people behave in reaction to a particular situation. These actions include bodily gestures and verbal sounds, showing responses to the situation playing out in front of them.

Mental processes in transitivity are also evident wherein journalists describe cognitive, affective, and perceptual experiences of an entity. These processes are related to the entity's internal consciousness and involve a single participant, the “senser”, and a phenomenon that is sensed. Samples from the corpora are the following:

“Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu is under significant pressure to do whatever is required to get the remaining hostages who are still alive.” (NA03)

“Tzafir believes the world should see that Hamas must be defeated so it is no longer a threat.” (NA05)

“Biden is eager to revisit Israel and deliver a speech before the country’s parliament.” (NA14)

These examples showcase mental processes related to transitivity by including the mental activities, perceptions, or attitudes of individuals involved. In the NA03, Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu is shown feeling the pressure, a state of mind, to make specific decisions about the hostages. In the same way, Tzafir shares his view on the need to defeat Hamas for the purpose of ensuring security in news article 5. In NA14, Biden's keenness to return to Israel and give a speech demonstrates his cognitive readiness to carry out a specific task. These mental activities pertain to the cognitive or emotional components of human perception instead of bodily movements.

Lastly, the existential process. The existential process in transitivity refers to a process that explains the existence of something, such as people, things, events, actions, or moments, which are referred to as existents. This process is characterized by the use of "there" as the subject and auxiliary verbs like "was" and "were" to indicate existence. Existential processes focus on the existence of entities or events and often involve circumstances like place, time, or manner. Excerpts below exemplifies existential process:

“...there is wide support among Palestinians for Hamas's deadly attacks on Israel which triggered it.” (NA05)

“There has been daily cross-border fire between Israel and Lebanon since the war in Gaza began. (NA13)

“There are casualties among the Israeli forces who dispersed the demonstrators at the Shuafat camp” (NA21)

The examples above demonstrate existential processes in transitivity by presenting the existence or presence of specific entities or situations without explicitly showing any actions. The primary focus in the excerpt from NA05 is on the broad backing among Palestinians for Hamas's lethal assaults. In NA13, the continual exchange of fire across the Israel-Lebanon border. In the third example (NA21), the focus is on the presence of casualties among the Israeli forces. In general, these sentences emphasize the existence of specific entities or situations.

Conclusions

To summarize, this study has shed light on the framing techniques journalists use to shape news stories about the Israel-Hamas conflict. Through examining framing techniques, morphosemantic, and syntactic features, the study has obtained an understanding of how language is used to form narratives and influence public discussions on geopolitical matters. The results of this research not only enhance the comprehension of how conflict is portrayed in media but also impact language instruction and media literacy education.

In the future, additional research could investigate how people receive and understand framed news, compare different linguistic and cultural contexts, monitor changes in media coverage over time, and use interdisciplinary methods to understand various aspects of news framing. By further examining how language influences perceptions, ideologies, and the dynamics in conflict coverage, we can enhance our comprehension of the complex relationship between language, media, and society.

This study adds to a wider conversation about how language influences our comprehension of worldwide conflicts and emphasizes the need for analyzing media communication critically. By promoting understanding of language tactics and framing methods, we can help people navigate modern media environments and participate in thoughtful discussions on urgent global issues.

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